

Theoretical dimensionless absolute value of the “astronomical unit” as a physical constant: God’s equation

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Since 2012, the astronomical Unit (abbreviated: 1au) relies on an international convention fixing its value at 149,597,870,700 meters [1]. The disadvantage of this constant is that it does not link to fundamental physical constants. The present letter remedies this disadvantage by establishing a more adequate derivation issuing from our new model of absolute dimensionless cosmology which aims to establish exact cosmological parameters. This model considers the astronomical unit as a fundamental physical constant, through its direct involvement with mathematical constants, and new cosmological parameters (not appearing in the current Λ CDM model). This new theoretical framework is the subject of a future publication of our work on dimensionless unified physics. The immediate object is to disclose the value described in the work. The absolute value of the dimensionless astronomical unit is fixed by the following irreducible numerical ratio:

$$\frac{1ua}{10^{11}m\grave{e}tres} = \frac{3\ 333\ 000\ 000}{8\ 537\ 866\ 152} \times \left(\left(13(\sqrt{15} - \sqrt{3}) \right) - 24 \right). \quad (1)$$

Ou,

$$1ua = 149\ 597\ 870\ 700.717\ 468\ 528\ 917\ 130\ 019\ 49\dots\dots meters. \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) shows that the astronomical unit of the year 2012 [1] diverges by:

$$0.717\ 468\ 528\ 917\ 130\ 019\ 49\dots\dots m\grave{e}tre \quad (3)$$

Or,

$$71.746\ 852\ 891\ 713\ 001\ 949\dots\dots cm. \quad (4)$$

This small discrepancy (of about 71.75 cm) from equation (4) (calculated relative to our purely theoretical exact value) confirms that the value adopted by the General Assembly of the International Astronomical Union is close to accuracy according to our model, thanks to its irreproachable precision given this great distance of: 149,597,870,700.717... km.

This study is part of our cosmological model which provides an answer to the Hubble tension, reconciling the Planck 2018 value and the SHOES value (Riess et al. 2019), and presents other discoveries, notably new cosmological parameters.

We are verifying our model using the 2018 Planck results while indicating that it has already allowed for the determination of the absolute values of the mean sidereal year and the mean sidereal day (available as a preprint on the ResearchGate platform).

A forthcoming letter describes a new equation for the 'parsec', also defined as a fundamental constant within our new cosmological model. In this new purely theoretical framework, the value of the parsec appears slightly lower than that in the current literature. This is a crucial step so that the parsec of scientific literature (which is not a fundamental constant) gives way to a new parsec having moreover the advantage of being an invariant and dimensionless fundamental physical constant.

In conclusion, our exact value of the astronomical unit transforms the 2012 convention into an absolute value stemming from an equation of an absolute cosmological model. This equation will be described later to pave the way for new advantages, both practical and theoretical.

References

[1] IAU 2012 Resolution B2 on the re-definition of the astronomical unit of length. XXVIIIth General Assembly of the International Astronomical Union, Beijing, China (2012).

[2] Jamil Kooli. An Irreducible Numerical Ratio for the Duration in Days of the Mean Sidereal Year via Ultimate Cosmology, Astronomy, and Astrophysics. ResearchGate. DOI:[10.13140/RG.2.2.20653.91361](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20653.91361).

[3] Jamil Kooli. An Absolutely Exact Duration in seconds of the Sidereal day, or Stellar day, emerging from an Irreducible Numerical Ratio from Ultimate Cosmology, Astronomy, and Astrophysics. ResearchGate. DOI:[10.13140/RG.2.2.23424.44805](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23424.44805).